

JUNIT 4 TUTORIAL

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Figure 1: The author Xavier NOUMBISSI NOUNDOU

1 Author's Biography

Xavier NOUMBISSI NOUNDOU is from CAMEROON and holds the title Diplom-Informatiker [DIPL.-INF.] ¹ (roughly equivalent to a canadian Master's degree in Computer Science) of the **University of Bremen** ² in Germany.

After his Diplom-Informatiker degree, he worked 18 months as Software Developer for **Siemens Healthcare** ³ in Erlangen (Germany).

After **Siemens**, Xavier started his doctoral research in Program Analysis and Software Engineering in the **Watform Lab** at the **University of Waterloo** ⁴ (Waterloo, Ontario, Canada).

From January 2012 to August 2012, Xavier worked in the Java J9-JIT compilation team of **IBM Toronto Lab.** in Markham (Ontario, Canada) as a graduate intern in compiler optimization.

Xavier is professionally proficient in the French, English and German languages.

For his DIPL.-INF. degree, Xavier worked on the automatic generation of test cases for reactive systems. The algorithms he developed are used by the German company

¹<http://www.inb.uni-luebeck.de/~boehme/diplinf.html>

²<http://www.uni-bremen.de>

³<http://www.healthcare.siemens.com>

⁴<http://www.uwaterloo.ca>

Verified Systems International GmbH⁵. The title of his diplom-informatiker thesis was "Statistical test cases generation for reactive systems".

Xavier currently works on his PhD degree. His research focuses on program analysis and software engineering. He is the creator of **SAINT**⁶, which is a tool to perform static taint analysis on programs written in the C programming language.

2 Introduction

The goal of this tutorial is to give an introduction to the JUnit [?, ?] framework that enables the reader to:

- Have a basic understanding of JUnit.
- Implement test classes in JUnit 4.
- Get coverage information from tests execution with Cobertura [?].
- Test exceptions using JUnit 4.

JUnit is a framework that helps in the automation of unit tests for Java classes. It was created by Kent Beck and Erich Gamma.

Similar tools exist for other languages such as C++ [?], Python [?], the .NET framework [?], etc.

Version 4 is the latest release of JUnit (as of writing). It is backward compatible with the previous version JUnit 3.8. In this tutorial, we only present the new conventions of JUnit 4.

JUnit 4 was released mainly to take advantages of the annotations capabilities introduced with Java 5.0 (JSR 175 [?]).

JUnit plugins are available for several Integrated Development Environment (IDE) like Eclipse, Netbeans, etc.

In this tutorial, we don't use any IDE for the demonstrations. We only run and collect test results from the command line.

3 Steps involved in performing unit tests

⁵<http://www.verified.de>

⁶<https://www.github.com/xaviernoumbis/saint>

- 1) Prepare (or set up) the test environment to fulfill conditions that must be met, according to the test plan. This means to define and set *prefix values* (e.g. initialize fields, turn on logging, etc.).
- 2) Execute the test case. It means exercising the part of the code to be tested. For that we use test inputs (*test case values*), according to the test plan.
- 3) Evaluate the results or side effects generated by the execution of the test case to check if they match what has been defined in the test plan.
- 4) Clean up (or tear down) the test environment if needed so that further testing activities can be done, without being influenced by the previous test cases. We deal here with *postfix values*.

4 How to Install JUnit 4

To use JUnit, you need to download the latest jar file from <http://junit.org> and include it in your classpath. As of writing, this file is `junit-4-8-1.jar`. JUnit can also be installed from most Linux distributions package manager. For instance, on Debian based distributions you can use the command:

```
sudo apt-get install junit4
```

5 How to Apply Unit Test Steps

Here we describe how the steps given in Section 3 are to be implemented in the JUnit framework. The different steps are implemented in a Java test class. The methods of the test class receive specific annotations to make them known to the framework as such:

- 1) Prepare (set up) the test environment: actions to realize this are to be implemented in one or several methods, annotated with `@Before`. These methods are then executed before each test case (test method).

```
@Before
public void setUp() {
    s = new Sample();
}
```

- 2) Execute the test case and evaluate the results (or side effects): This is done by exercising the code under test with test values in a test method. Each method annotated with `@Test` will be executed as a test case by JUnit. Evaluation of the expected results is done in the same method using assertions.

```

@Test
public void testAddition() {
    int a = 3, b = 6;
    int expectedOutput = (a+b);
    int res = s.Addition(a, b);
    assertEquals(expectedOutput, res);
}

```

- 3) Clean up (tear down) the test environment is done in one or several methods, that are run after execution of each test method. To belong to this group, a method has to be annotated with `@After`.

```

@After
public void tearDown() {
    s = null;
}

```

6 How to Run Test Cases

The JUnit 4 framework provides the class `org.junit.runner.JUnitCore` (a so called *Test Runner*) in order to run the tests and collect their results. The tests can be run from a Java program using the method `org.junit.runner.JUnitCore.runClasses()`.

The tests can also be run from the command line with:

```
java org.junit.runner.JUnitCore TestSample
```

The results are printed to the console:

```
JUnit version 4.8.1
....I
Time: 0.006
```

```
OK (4 tests)
```

For a failing test, the following is printed:

```
JUnit version 4.8.1
..E..I
Time: 0.011
There was 1 failure:
1) testPrintAddition(TestSample)
org.junit.ComparisonFailure: expected:<[8]
> but was:<[9]
>
```

```
at org.junit.Assert.assertEquals(Assert.java:123)
...
at TestSample.testPrintAddition(TestSample.java:113)
...
at org.junit.runner.JUnitCore.main(JUnitCore.java:45)
```

FAILURES!!!

Tests run: 4, Failures: 1

When using a plugin from within an IDE (such as Eclipse) results are generally printed in a GUI.

7 Unit Test Coverage Information

Figure 2: Coverage Tool in the Unit Testing Process

Generally, one may want to gain information about parts of the Unit Under Test that was exercised. For that you may want to use a tool to get coverage information.

Figure 2 illustrates this process.

Coverage tools instrument (add instructions to the unit under test to gather coverage information) your code before you execute the test cases. Then, when the test cases are run, information about what part of the code was executed is written to a file (created by the tool).

Then you can call the coverage tool to visualize parts of the code that were executed. These tools usually have a graphic user interface.

In the following we present the coverage tool Cobertura.

8 What is Cobertura

Cobertura is a coverage tool for Java. Here are some features from the tool website (cobertura.sourceforge.net):

- Can be executed from ant or from the command line.
- Instruments Java bytecode after it has been compiled.
- Can generate reports in HTML or XML.
- Shows the percentage of lines and branches covered for each class, each package, and for the overall project.
- Shows the McCabe cyclomatic code complexity of each class, and the average cyclomatic code complexity for each package, and for the overall product.
- Can sort HTML results by class name, percent of lines covered, percent of branches covered, etc. It can sort in ascending or descending order.

Steps in using Cobertura with JUnit from the command line:

1) Compile your java classes:

```
javac Sample.java TestSample.java
```

2) Instrument the class files of the code you want to gather coverage information:

```
cobertura-instrument.sh Sample.class
```

3) Execute your unit tests:

```
java org.junit.runner.JUnitCore TestSample
```

4) Generate coverage information:

```
cobertura-report.sh --destination <report directory>
```

This action generates HTML files in the folder <report directory>, that contains tests coverage information.

9 How to Install Cobertura

To use Cobertura, download its latest distribution file from cobertura.sourceforge.net. After unpacking the archive, the location of the folder has to be included in the executable path.

For example on Linux based machines using a Bourne shell (Bash):

```
export PATH=<Cobertura directory>:$PATH
```

For how to use other features and commands of Cobertura, please refer to the tool website.

10 How to Test an Exception

For testing Exceptions thrown by a method, we present two mechanisms. The first mechanism was created with JUnit 4: its use requires the use of the annotation `@Test` with the attribute `expected`:

```
@Test(expected=ArithmeticException.class)
public void testDivideByZero() {
    s.divideByZero();
}
```

However, if a developer wants to access details information about the exception instance, he should rather use the older method from JUnit 3. In that case the method `org.junit.Assert.fail()` can be used to trigger failure of a test. This can be desirable in cases where the expected exception was not thrown.

```
@Test
public void testAnotherException() {
    try{
        s.anotherException(0);
        //With the method fail, we can signalize to
        //the framework that the test failed.
        fail("MyException was not thrown!");
    }
    catch(MyException e) {
        //Here we have access to more info
        assertNotNull(e.getMessage());
    }
}
```

11 How to Ignore a Test

JUnit gives also the possibility not to execute a test method. For that, the method has to be annotated with `@Ignore`. This may be desirable for instance in cases where a test method is incomplete.

```
@Ignore("Not Ready, to be changed")
@Test
public void doNothing() {
}
```

12 How to Build a Test Suite

To group test cases into test suites, a suite class has to be defined. The annotation `@Suite.SuiteClasses` is used to specify the test classes to be incorporated to the suite.

```
import org.junit.runner.RunWith;
import org.junit.runners.Suite;

@RunWith(Suite.class)
@Suite.SuiteClasses({ TestSample.class , TestOther.class })
public class MySuite {
}
```